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MINI REVIEW

Neuroprotective Effects of Thiazolidine-4-Carboxylic Acid Derivatives on Memory Impairment and Neurodegeneration

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ABSTRACT

Some studies have shown numerous biological activities of Thiazolidine derivatives, including neuroprotection. The production of inflammatory markers and Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS) plays a major role in nerve damage that leads to memory impairment. Several studies have shown that alcohol consumption impairs memory in adults. However, the underlying mechanism is still unclear. Ethanol treatment also leads to memory impairment in mice. Exposure to ambient pollutants such as air pollutants also can be adversely impacted the Central Nervous System (CNS) by the activation of proinflammatory pathways and reactive oxygen species. Thus, targeting neuroinflammation and oxidative distress can be a useful strategy to eliminate the obvious symptoms of neurodegeneration. In addition, treatment with Thiazolidine-4-Carboxylic Acid derivatives reduces oxidative stress, neuroinflammation, and ethanol-induced memory impairment. In general, Thiazolidine derivatives may be useful in reducing neuroinflammation by acting on different stages of inflammation. In the current mini-review, we examined the neuroprotective potential of these compounds in a model of ethanol-induced neuritis.

INTRODUCTION

It is estimated that 20 - 70 % of urban air pollutants are resulting from traffic combustion [1,2] and 85% of Particulate Matter (PM) in urban areas is related to traffic [3]. New evidence suggests that air pollution exposure has been known as one of the main sources of neuroinflammation and oxidative stress, causing CNS and neuropathology disease [4-6]. Activation of ROS and pro-inflammatory pathways by PM is thought to elicit maladaptive responses that can in turn adversely impact organ function and the CNS also isn't immune to air pollution impact [4,7,8]. There are several pathways via which can be transmitted inflammatory signals from environment to brain [5], so in people exposed to urban air pollutants, activation of the peripheral immune system may lead to neuroinflammation [9]. Neuroinflammatory reactions are triggered by oxidative stress, cytokines, and chemokines and can lead to impaired neurotransmitter and neurotrophin signaling disorders, abnormal protein accumulation, neurodegeneration, and neuronal remodeling [10]. Prolonged exposure to these pollutants may lead to an increase in the inflammatory markers upregulation and exacerbate previous neurodegenerative disorders [11-14]. In addition, new findings support the involvement of neuroinflammation in the pathogenesis of emotional and cognitive disorders [15,16]. Neurodegenerative Diseases (NDs) pose a greater risk to humans, more precisely to the elderly population [17], and according to the WHO, it will

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overtake cancer in the next 20 years [18]. These diseases include a number of neurological disorders characterized by a diverse array of pathophysiology and are associated with cognitive impairment and/or mobility impairment [19]. It includes a wide range of disorders, the two most common of which are Parkinson's Disease (PD) and Alzheimer's Disease (AD) [20]. Neurodegenerative diseases are common to many of the major processes associated with dysfunction and neuronal death, including oxidative stress and the formation of free radicals, neuroinflammation, protein folding and malformation, bioenergy disorders, and mitochondrial dysfunction [21]. Many Thiazolidines are available as potential clinical drugs against many diseases; such as rosiglitazone (antidiabetic), pioglitazone (antidiabetic), etozoline (loop diuretic), teneligliptin (antidiabetic), benzylpenicillin (antibiotic), and raltoline (anticonvulsant) [22]. Despite the high prevalence, limited or no Disease-Modifying Therapy (DMT) is available to manage these disorders, thus emphasizing the significant translation gap from drug development to *in vivo* experimentation and to clinical trials [24]. Several heterocyclic components such as Thiazolidines, exhibit favorable biological activity due to the inherent structural diversity that provides structure modulation to a greater extent [24]. Considering the antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and neuroprotective properties of Thiazolidine derivatives, here in this brief review, we evaluate the effect of Thiazolidine-4-Carboxylic Acid on oxidative stress and neuroinflammation.

Neuroprotective effects of Thiazolidine-4-Carboxylic Acid derivatives

Many Thiazolidines are screened for potential anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer, anti-viral, anti-microbial, neuroprotective, acetyl / butyrylcholinesterase inhibitory, analgesic, hepatic protective, and immunostimulatory properties [22,25]. Several reports have shown that these compounds are likely to have strong free radical scavenging properties [26,27] which can be attributed to neuroprotection in Parkinson's [28] Alzheimer's [29] and other models of memory impairment [30]. In this regard, the beneficial effects of Thiazolidines against various Alzheimer's targets have been recently reviewed [31,32]. Previously reported mechanistic studies showed that Thiazolidines mediate anti-inflammatory effects by inhibition of NF- κ B [33]. Neuroinflammation is a common feature of all neurological disorders caused by oxidative stress and excites altered neuronal function [34,35]. Increased inflammatory mediators and cytokines cause macrophages to penetrate the brain, which intensifies the underlying pathogenesis [36]. Similarly, other research studies have suggested the role of inflammatory cascades in the pathophysiology of various neurodegenerative models not only in laboratory animals but also in postmortem brain samples [37,38]. In addition, inflammatory cytokines cause behavioral and cognitive impairments [39] disrupts the metabolism of neurotransmitters and reduces nerve flexibility [40,41].

Behavioral and cognitive alteration by ethanol consumption in humans is replicated in animal rodent models [42]. In addition, alcohol consumption can exacerbate the underlying pathology of many neurological disorders such as Alzheimer's disease, memory loss, and depression [43] both by expediting cytokines release and also compromises the endogenous antioxidant defense system [44] and therefore can cause neuronal death with either apoptosis or necrosis (or even both) [45]. As mentioned in most scientific texts, the ethanol-induced nerve damage model is widely used because it covers most aspects of memory impairment and neuroinflammation [46,47]. Inflammation of NLRP3 plays an important role in innate immunity and is, therefore, the inflammasome has been investigated [48]. Mitochondrial dysfunction has been suggested to accelerate neurodegeneration due to increased production of Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS) and inflammatory activation of NLRP3 in neurodegenerative and other inflammatory diseases [49]. Activation of NLRP3 inflammation involves a two-step process. First, activation of the Nuclear Factor-kappa B (NF- κ B) pathway is required to upregulate the expression of pro-interleukin-1 β (pro-IL-1 β), NLRP3, and caspase-1, which is accomplished by stimulation of TLRs (Toll-Like Receptors) [50,51]. After priming, the NLRP3 complex can be activated by several stimuli, including extracellular ATP, lysosomal rupture, ROS, and ionic flux [52].

The effect of Thiazolidine-4-Carboxylic Acid on oxidative stress and neuroinflammation

Thiazolidine core has been reported in recent years due to their high pharmacological activity in many pharmaceutical formulations [22]. More interestingly, these molecules have a variety of uses and are marketed as potential candidate drugs against various disorders. Due to their pharmacological significance, including immune history and permeability of the Blood-Brain Barrier (BBB), some Thiazolidine-4-Carboxylic Acid derivatives can target several stages of the inflammatory cascade. The reason for significant antioxidant activity is the presence of phenolic moiety in the structure of Thiazolidine-4-Carboxylic Acid derivatives. Phenolic compounds have strong antioxidant properties, and many natural compounds with a phenolic moiety consistently exhibit favorable biological activity. In addition, the use of compounds containing the structural part of phenol has been extensively studied in the treatment of neurodegenerative diseases such as Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease and Huntington's disease [53,54].

The neuroprotective role of Thiazolidine-4-Carboxylic Acid derivatives in an ethanol-induced neurodegenerative model has been demonstrated. These complex cascades reduce the inflammation caused by oxidative stress. Most neurodegenerative disorders are characterized by complex pathophysiology due to the complex nature of the brain, and for this reason, several drugs have been tested in animal experimental models, but no drugs are eligible for clinical

trials [55]. Consistent human data reiterated the generation of free radicals with ethanol consumption [44], and such amassing precipitated cognitive impairment due to narrow anti-oxidants in the brain [56]. Ethanol has a high propensity for ROS generation and this is further validated by an elevated level of LPO along with a reduced glutathione level and which is consistent with previous findings [35]. Many published reports are evident of showing the relationship between oxidative stress and stimulation of inflammatory cascades [57,58]. Increased oxidative stress and lower levels of antioxidant enzymes may have critical effects on brain tissues [59]. The Thiazolidine derivatives have been tremendous potential to attenuate memory impairment and neuroinflammation [28].

Therefore, successful treatment approaches should aim to control neuroinflammation as well as reduce oxidative stress by stimulating antioxidant enzymes. Several studies have reported the antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activity of Thiazolidine derivatives [25-27]. GSH, GST and catalase play a tremendous role in suppressing free radicals [60]. Numerous Thiazolidine derivatives have been reported as antioxidants through GSH activation and LPO inhibition [61]. Neuroinflammation causes the release of ROS, which is responsible for oxidative stress and which aids to intensify the pathogenesis of neurological diseases such as memory impairment, cognitive deficits and other behavioral disorders [62]. Activation of NLRP3 inflammation is associated with the development of several inflammatory diseases and disorders, especially those related to age, such as Alzheimer's disease and Type II Diabetes (T2D) [63,64]. The release of ROS and proinflammatory mediators such as Tumor Necrosis Factor-Alpha (TNF- α), Interleukin-1 (IL-1 β) leads to cellular damage and lipid peroxidation [65]. In a neurodegenerative brain, TNF- α -induced NF- κ B plays a central role in regulating inflammation following different transcription and transmission pathways [66]. According to the research reports, the activation of NF- κ B inflammatory pathways is directly related to the attachment of TNF- α to its respective receptor [67]. Inhibition of TNF- α helps to alleviate not only inflammation but also cognitive deficits. In addition, molecular binding studies against several targets involved in neuroinflammation such as NF- κ B, NLRP3, TLR4, and COX-2 also show neuroprotective effects of synthesized compounds [68]. Findings advise that Thiazolidine derivatives can reduce neuronal damage through down regulating the overexpression of proinflammatory cytokines and further by modulating the p-NF- κ B and NLRP3 pathways.

CONCLUSION

Neuronal damage exposed to ambient pollutants and or ethanol consumption activates several proinflammatory cytokines, including TNF- α , NF- κ B, NLRP3, and COX-2, and is predominantly associated with oxidative stress. Thiazolidine-4-Carboxylic Acid derivatives reverse

oxidative stress and the inflammatory cascade of ethanol exposure by possibly reducing the ROS/NF- κ B/NLRP3/TNF- α /COX-2 cascade, which ultimately leads to their neuroprotective role against neurodegenerative diseases.

REFERENCES

- Geller MD, Sardar SB, Phuleria H, Fine PM, Sioutas C. Measurements of particle number and mass concentrations and size distributions in a tunnel environment. *Environ Sci Technol*. 2005 Nov 15;39(22):8653-8663. doi: 10.1021/es050360s. PMID: 16323759.
- Lanki T. Can we identify sources of fine particles responsible for exercise-induced ischemia on days with elevated air pollution? The ULTRA study. *Environmental Health Perspectives*. 2006;114(5):655. <https://tinyurl.com/yeystxf2>
- Jonidi Jafari A, Ehsanifar. The share of different vehicles in air pollutant emission in tehran, using 2013 traffic information. *Caspian Journal of Health Research*. 2016;2(2):28-36. <https://tinyurl.com/5n6tyk6y>
- Ehsanifar M, Banihashemian, Farokhmanesh. Exposure to urban air pollution nanoparticles and CNS disease. *On J Neur & Br Disord*. 2021;5(5):520-526. <https://tinyurl.com/yckpyvvy>
- Ehsanifar M, Tameh AA, Farzadkia M, Kalantari RR, Zavareh MS, Nikzaad H, Jafari AJ. Exposure to nanoscale diesel exhaust particles: Oxidative stress, neuroinflammation, anxiety and depression on adult male mice. *Ecotoxicol Environ Saf*. 2019 Jan 30;168:338-347. doi: 10.1016/j.ecoenv.2018.10.090. Epub 2018 Nov 2. PMID: 30391838.
- Ehsanifar M, Jafari AJ, Nikzad H, Zavareh MS, Atlasi MA, Mohammadi H, Tameh AA. Prenatal exposure to diesel exhaust particle
- s causes anxiety, spatial memory disorders with alters expression of hippocampal pro-inflammatory cytokines and NMDA receptor subunits in adult male mice offspring. *Ecotoxicol Environ Saf*. 2019 Jul 30;176:34-41. doi: 10.1016/j.ecoenv.2019.03.090. Epub 2019 Mar 25. PMID: 30921694.
- Ehsanifar M, Banihashemian. Exposure to air pollution nanoparticles: Oxidative stress and neuroinflammation. *J Biomed Res Environ Sci*. 2021;2(10):964-976. <https://tinyurl.com/ykdbc6a7>
- Ehsanifar M, Banihashemian, Farokhmanesh. Exposure to ambient ultra-fine particles and stroke. 2021. <https://tinyurl.com/2p9ebx6e>
- Brook RD, Rajagopalan S, Pope CA 3rd, Brook JR, Bhatnagar A, Diez-Roux AV, Holguin F, Hong Y, Luepker RV, Mittleman MA, Peters A, Siscovick D, Smith SC Jr, Whitsett L, Kaufman JD; American Heart Association Council on Epidemiology and Prevention, Council on the Kidney in Cardiovascular Disease, and Council on Nutrition, Physical Activity and Metabolism. Particulate matter air pollution and cardiovascular disease: An update to the scientific statement from the American Heart Association. *Circulation*. 2010 Jun 1;121(21):2331-2378. doi: 10.1161/CIR.0b013e3181d8ce1. Epub 2010 May 10. PMID: 20458016.
- Teeling JL, Perry VH. Systemic infection and inflammation in acute CNS injury and chronic neurodegeneration: underlying mechanisms. *Neuroscience*. 2009 Feb 6;158(3):1062-1073. doi: 10.1016/j.neuroscience.2008.07.031. Epub 2008 Jul 25. PMID: 18706982.
- Godbout JP, Chen J, Abraham J, Richwine AF, Berg BM, Kelley KW, Johnson RW. Exaggerated neuroinflammation and sickness behavior in aged mice following activation of the peripheral innate immune system. *FASEB J*. 2005 Aug;19(10):1329-1331. doi: 10.1096/fj.05-3776je. Epub 2005 May 26. PMID: 15919760.
- Cunningham C, Campion S, Lunnon K, Murray CL, Woods JF, Deacon RM, Rawlins JN, Perry VH. Systemic inflammation induces acute behavioral and cognitive changes and accelerates neurodegenerative disease. *Biol Psychiatry*. 2009 Feb 15;65(4):304-312. doi: 10.1016/j.biopsych.2008.07.024. Epub 2008 Sep 18. PMID: 18801476; PMCID: PMC2633437.
- Ehsanifar M, Montazeri Z, Taheri MA, Rafati M, Behjati M, Karimian M. Hippocampal inflammation and oxidative stress following exposure to diesel exhaust nanoparticles in male and female mice. *Neurochem Int*. 2021 May;145:104989. doi: 10.1016/j.neuint.2021.104989. Epub 2021 Feb 12. PMID: 33582162.
- Ehsanifar M. Airborne aerosols particles and COVID-19 transition. *Environ Res*. 2021 Sep;200:111752. doi: 10.1016/j.envres.2021.111752. Epub 2021 Jul 22. PMID: 34302822; PMCID: PMC8295061.
- Clark IA, Alleva LM, Vissel B. The roles of TNF in brain dysfunction and disease. *Pharmacol Ther*. 2010 Dec;128(3):519-548. doi: 10.1016/j.pharmthera.2010.08.007. Epub 2010 Sep 8. PMID: 20813131.
- Ehsanifar M, Jafari AJ, Montazeri Z, Kalantari RR, Gholami M, Ashtarinezhad A. Learning and memory disorders related to hippocampal inflammation following

- exposure to air pollution. *J Environ Health Sci Eng.* 2021 Jan 22;19(1):261-272. doi: 10.1007/s40201-020-00600-x. PMID: 34150234; PMCID: PMC8172730.
18. Heemels MT. Neurodegenerative diseases. *Nature.* 2016 Nov 10;539(7628):179. doi: 10.1038/539179a. PMID: 27830810.
 19. Durães F, Pinto M, Sousa E. Old drugs as new treatments for neurodegenerative diseases. *Pharmaceuticals (Basel).* 2018 May 11;11(2):44. doi: 10.3390/ph11020044. PMID: 29751602; PMCID: PMC6027455.
 20. Akhtar A, Andleeb A, Waris TS, Bazzar M, Moradi AR, Awan NR, Yar M. Neurodegenerative diseases and effective drug delivery: A review of challenges and novel therapeutics. *J Control Release.* 2021 Feb 10;330:1152-1167. doi: 10.1016/j.jconrel.2020.11.021. Epub 2020 Nov 13. PMID: 33197487.
 21. Brettschneider J, Del Tredici K, Lee VM, Trojanowski JQ. Spreading of pathology in neurodegenerative diseases: a focus on human studies. *Nat Rev Neurosci.* 2015 Feb;16(2):109-120. doi: 10.1038/nrn3887. Epub 2015 Jan 15. PMID: 25588378; PMCID: PMC4312418.
 22. Gitler AD, Dhillon, Shorter. Neurodegenerative disease: models, mechanisms, and a new hope. 2017:499-502. <https://tinyurl.com/mtpf2k97>
 23. Sahiba N, Sethiya A, Soni J, Agarwal DK, Agarwal S. Saturated five-membered thiazolidines and their derivatives: from synthesis to biological applications. *Top Curr Chem (Cham).* 2020 Mar 23;378(2):34. doi: 10.1007/s41061-020-0298-4. PMID: 32206929; PMCID: PMC7101601.
 24. Vuong T, Mallet JF, Ouzounova M, Rahbar S, Hernandez-Vargas H, Herceg Z, Matar C. Role of a polyphenol-enriched preparation on chemoprevention of mammary carcinoma through cancer stem cells and inflammatory pathways modulation. *J Transl Med.* 2016 Jan 14;14:13. doi: 10.1186/s12967-016-0770-7. PMID: 26762586; PMCID: PMC4712588.
 25. Lu Y, Li CM, Wang Z, Ross CR 2nd, Chen J, Dalton JT, Li W, Miller DD. Discovery of 4-substituted methoxybenzoyl-aryl-thiazole as novel anticancer agents: Synthesis, biological evaluation, and structure-activity relationships. *J Med Chem.* 2009 Mar 26;52(6):1701-1711. doi: 10.1021/jm801449a. PMID: 19243174; PMCID: PMC2760094.
 26. Abdellatif KR, Abdelgawad MA, Elshemy HA, Alsayed SS. Design, synthesis and biological screening of new 4-thiazolidinone derivatives with promising COX-2 selectivity, anti-inflammatory activity and gastric safety profile. *Bioorg Chem.* 2016 Feb;64:1-12. doi: 10.1016/j.bioorg.2015.11.001. Epub 2015 Nov 6. PMID: 26561742.
 27. Marc G. New phenolic derivatives of thiazolidine-2, 4-dione with antioxidant and antiradical properties: synthesis, characterization, in vitro evaluation, and quantum studies. *Molecules.* 2019;24(11):2060. <https://tinyurl.com/4vsyyb97>
 28. Ham YH, Jason Chan KK, Chan W. Thioproline serves as an efficient antioxidant protecting human cells from oxidative stress and improves cell viability. *Chem Res Toxicol.* 2020 Jul 20;33(7):1815-1821. doi: 10.1021/acs.chemrestox.0c00055. Epub 2020 Apr 30. PMID: 32299210.
 29. Wang XK, Sun T, Li YJ, Wang YH, Li YJ, Yang LD, Feng D, Zhao MG, Wu YM. A novel thiazolidinediones ATZD2 rescues memory deficits in a rat model of type 2 diabetes through antioxidant and antiinflammation. *Oncotarget.* 2017 Nov 18;8(64):107409-107422. doi: 10.18632/oncotarget.22467. PMID: 29296174; PMCID: PMC5746076.
 30. Sadashiva CT, Chandra JN, Kavitha CV, Thimmegowda A, Subhash MN, Rangappa KS. Synthesis and pharmacological evaluation of novel N-alkyl/aryl substituted thiazolidinone arecoline analogues as muscarinic receptor 1 agonist in Alzheimer's dementia models. *Eur J Med Chem.* 2009 Dec;44(12):4848-4854. doi: 10.1016/j.ejmech.2009.07.026. Epub 2009 Aug 6. PMID: 19717214.
 31. Zhao L, Huang W, Liu H, Wang L, Zhong W, Xiao J, Hu Y, Li S. FK506-binding protein ligands: Structure-based design, synthesis, and neurotrophic/neuroprotective properties of substituted 5,5-dimethyl-2-(4-thiazolidine)carboxylates. *J Med Chem.* 2006 Jul 13;49(14):4059-4071. doi: 10.1021/jm0502384. PMID: 16821768.
 32. Kumar B, Mantha Kumar. Recent developments on the structure-activity relationship studies of MAO inhibitors and their role in different neurological disorders. *RSC advances.* 2016;6(48):42660-42683. <https://tinyurl.com/4nwwya8p>
 33. Gandini A, Bartolini M, Tedesco D, Martinez-Gonzalez L, Roca C, Campillo NE, Zaldivar-Diez J, Perez C, Zuccheri G, Miti A, Feoli A, Castellano S, Petralla S, Monti B, Rossi M, Moda F, Legname G, Martinez A, Bolognesi ML. Tau-centric multitarget approach for alzheimer's disease: development of first-in-class dual glycogen synthase kinase 3 β and tau-aggregation inhibitors. *J Med Chem.* 2018 Sep 13;61(17):7640-7656. doi: 10.1021/acs.jmedchem.8b00610. Epub 2018 Aug 24. PMID: 30078314.
 34. Kaplan J, Nowell M, Chima R, Zingarelli B. Pioglitazone reduces inflammation through inhibition of NF- κ B in polymicrobial sepsis. *Innate Immun.* 2014 Jul;20(5):519-28. doi: 10.1177/1753425913501565. Epub 2013 Sep 12. PMID: 24029145; PMCID: PMC3954463.
 35. Ali T, Badshah H, Kim TH, Kim MO. Melatonin attenuates D-galactose-induced memory impairment, neuroinflammation and neurodegeneration via RAGE/NF- κ B/JNK signaling pathway in aging mouse model. *J Pineal Res.* 2015 Jan;58(1):71-85. doi: 10.1111/jpi.12194. Epub 2014 Dec 9. PMID: 25401971.
 36. Imran M, Al Kury LT, Nadeem H, Shah FA, Abbas M, Naz S, Khan AU, Li S. Benzimidazole containing acetamide derivatives attenuate neuroinflammation and oxidative stress in ethanol-induced neurodegeneration. *Biomolecules.* 2020 Jan 8;10(1):108. doi: 10.3390/biom10010108. PMID: 31936383; PMCID: PMC7023260.
 37. Yin J, Valin KL, Dixon ML, Leavenworth JW. The role of microglia and macrophages in CNS homeostasis, autoimmunity, and cancer. *J Immunol Res.* 2017;2017:5150678. doi: 10.1155/2017/5150678. Epub 2017 Dec 19. PMID: 29410971; PMCID: PMC5749282.
 38. Dean B, Tawadros N, Scarr E, Gibbons AS. Regionally-specific changes in levels of tumour necrosis factor in the dorsolateral prefrontal cortex obtained postmortem from subjects with major depressive disorder. *J Affect Disord.* 2010 Jan;120(1-3):245-248. doi: 10.1016/j.jad.2009.04.027. PMID: 19446343.
 39. Rao JS, Rapoport SI, Kim HW. Altered neuroinflammatory, arachidonic acid cascade and synaptic markers in postmortem Alzheimer's disease brain. *Transl Psychiatry.* 2011 Aug 16;1(8):e31. doi: 10.1038/tp.2011.27. Retraction in: *Transl Psychiatry.* 2017 May 9;7(5):e1127. PMID: 22832605; PMCID: PMC3309508.
 40. Ben Menachem-Zidon O, Goshen I, Kreisel T, Ben Menahem Y, Reinhartz E, Ben Hur T, Yirmiya R. Intrahippocampal transplantation of transgenic neural precursor cells overexpressing interleukin-1 receptor antagonist blocks chronic isolation-induced impairment in memory and neurogenesis. *Neuropsychopharmacology.* 2008 Aug;33(9):2251-2262. doi: 10.1038/sj.npp.1301606. Epub 2007 Nov 7. PMID: 17987063.
 41. Goshen I, Kreisel T, Ben-Menachem-Zidon O, Licht T, Weidenfeld J, Ben-Hur T, Yirmiya R. Brain interleukin-1 mediates chronic stress-induced depression in mice via adrenocortical activation and hippocampal neurogenesis suppression. *Mol Psychiatry.* 2008 Jul;13(7):717-728. doi: 10.1038/sj.mp.4002055. Epub 2007 Aug 14. PMID: 17700577.
 42. Ehsanifar M, Montazeri, Rafati. Alzheimer's disease-like neuropathology following exposure to ambient noise. *J Biomed Res Environ Sci.* 2021;2(11):1159-1162. <https://tinyurl.com/yevheu6b>
 43. Ali T. Acute dose of melatonin via Nrf2 dependently prevents acute ethanol-induced neurotoxicity in the developing rodent brain. *Journal of neuroinflammation.* 2018;15(1):1-19. <https://tinyurl.com/y5u66wft>
 44. Eckardt MJ, File SE, Gessa GL, Grant KA, Guerri C, Hoffman PL, Kalant H, Koob GF, Li TK, Tabakoff B. Effects of moderate alcohol consumption on the central nervous system. *Alcohol Clin Exp Res.* 1998 Aug;22(5):998-1040. doi: 10.1111/j.1530-0277.1998.tb03695.x. PMID: 9726269.
 45. Reddy VD, Padmavathi P, Kavitha G, Saradamma B, Varadacharyulu N. Alcohol-induced oxidative/nitrosative stress alters brain mitochondrial membrane properties. *Mol Cell Biochem.* 2013 Mar;375(1-2):39-47. doi: 10.1007/s11010-012-1526-1. Epub 2012 Dec 1. PMID: 23212448.
 46. Vallés SL, Blanco AM, Pascual M, Guerri C. Chronic ethanol treatment enhances inflammatory mediators and cell death in the brain and in astrocytes. *Brain Pathol.* 2004 Oct;14(4):365-371. doi: 10.1111/j.1750-3639.2004.tb00079.x. PMID: 15605983; PMCID: PMC8095743.
 47. Saito M, Chakraborty G, Hui M, Masiello K, Saito M. Ethanol-induced neurodegeneration and glial activation in the developing brain. *Brain Sci.* 2016 Aug 16;6(3):31. doi: 10.3390/brainsci6030031. PMID: 27537918; PMCID: PMC5039460.
 48. Al Kury LT, Zeb A, Abidin ZU, Irshad N, Malik I, Alvi AM, Khalil AAK, Ahmad S, Faheem M, Khan AU, Shah FA, Li S. Neuroprotective effects of melatonin and celecoxib against ethanol-induced neurodegeneration: a computational and pharmacological approach. *Drug Des Devel Ther.* 2019 Aug 2;13:2715-2727. doi: 10.2147/DDDT.S207310. PMID: 31447548; PMCID: PMC6683968.
 49. Franchi L, Eigenbrod T, Muñoz-Planillo R, Núñez G. The inflammasome: A caspase-1-activation platform that regulates immune responses and disease pathogenesis. *Nat Immunol.* 2009 Mar;10(3):241-247. doi: 10.1038/ni.1703. PMID: 19221555; PMCID: PMC2820724.
 50. Gong Z, Pan J, Shen Q, Li M, Peng Y. Mitochondrial dysfunction induces NLRP3 inflammasome activation during cerebral ischemia/reperfusion injury. *J Neuroinflammation.* 2018 Aug 28;15(1):242. doi: 10.1186/s12974-018-1282-6. PMID: 30153825; PMCID: PMC6114292.
 51. Toma C, Higa N, Koizumi Y, Nakasone N, Ogura Y, McCoy AJ, Franchi L, Uematsu S, Sagara J, Taniguchi S, Tsutsui H, Akira S, Tschopp J, Núñez G, Suzuki T. Pathogenic *Vibrio* activate NLRP3 inflammasome via cytotoxins and TLR/nucleotide-binding oligomerization domain-mediated NF- κ B signaling. *J Immunol.* 2010 May 1;184(9):5287-5297. doi: 10.4049/jimmunol.0903536. Epub 2010 Mar 26. PMID: 20348425.
 52. Qiao Y, Wang P, Qi J, Zhang L, Gao C. TLR-induced NF- κ B activation regulates NLRP3 expression in murine macrophages. *FEBS Lett.* 2012 Apr 5;586(7):1022-1026. doi:

- 10.1016/j.febslet.2012.02.045. Epub 2012 Mar 8. PMID: 22569257.
53. Muñoz-Planillo R, Kuffa P, Martínez-Colón G, Smith BL, Rajendiran TM, Núñez G. K₁₈ efflux is the common trigger of NLRP3 inflammasome activation by bacterial toxins and particulate matter. *Immunity*. 2013 Jun 27;38(6):1142-1153. doi: 10.1016/j.immuni.2013.05.016. PMID: 23809161; PMCID: PMC3730833.
54. Pisoschi AM, Pop A. The role of antioxidants in the chemistry of oxidative stress: A review. *Eur J Med Chem*. 2015 Jun 5;97:55-74. doi: 10.1016/j.ejmech.2015.04.040. Epub 2015 Apr 22. PMID: 25942353.
55. Neha K, Haider MR, Pathak A, Yar MS. Medicinal prospects of antioxidants: A review. *Eur J Med Chem*. 2019 Sep 15;178:687-704. doi: 10.1016/j.ejmech.2019.06.010. Epub 2019 Jun 13. PMID: 31228811.
56. Van der Schyf CJ. The use of multi-target drugs in the treatment of neurodegenerative diseases. *Expert Rev Clin Pharmacol*. 2011 May;4(3):293-298. doi: 10.1586/ecp.11.13. PMID: 22114774.
57. Salim S. Oxidative stress and the central nervous system. *J Pharmacol Exp Ther*. 2017 Jan;360(1):201-205. doi: 10.1124/jpet.116.237503. Epub 2016 Oct 17. PMID: 27754930; PMCID: PMC5193071.
58. Hassanzadeh K, Rahimmi. Oxidative stress and neuroinflammation in the story of Parkinson's disease: could targeting these pathways write a good ending? *Journal of cellular physiology*. 2019;234(1):23-32. <https://tinyurl.com/3sd5ssn9>
59. He J, Zhu G, Wang G, Zhang F. Oxidative stress and neuroinflammation potentiate each other to promote progression of dopamine neurodegeneration. *Oxid Med Cell Longev*. 2020 Jul 3;2020:6137521. doi: 10.1155/2020/6137521. PMID: 32714488; PMCID: PMC7354668.
60. Gu F, Zhu M, Shi J, Hu Y, Zhao Z. Enhanced oxidative stress is an early event during development of Alzheimer-like pathologies in presenilin conditional knock-out mice. *Neurosci Lett*. 2008 Jul 25;440(1):44-48. doi: 10.1016/j.neulet.2008.05.050. Epub 2008 May 18. PMID: 18539391.
61. Lee KH, Cha M, Lee BH. Neuroprotective Effect of Antioxidants in the Brain. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2020 Sep 28;21(19):7152. doi: 10.3390/ijms21197152. PMID: 32998277; PMCID: PMC7582347.
62. Bayram FEÖ. The cysteine releasing pattern of some antioxidant thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acids. *European journal of medicinal chemistry*. 2016;114:337-344. <https://tinyurl.com/2p8schec>
63. Pascual M, Blanco AM, Cauli O, Miñarro J, Guerri C. Intermittent ethanol exposure induces inflammatory brain damage and causes long-term behavioural alterations in adolescent rats. *Eur J Neurosci*. 2007 Jan;25(2):541-550. doi: 10.1111/j.1460-9568.2006.05298.x. PMID: 17284196.
64. Halle A, Hornung V, Petzold GC, Stewart CR, Monks BG, Reinheckel T, Fitzgerald KA, Latz E, Moore KJ, Golenbock DT. The NALP3 inflammasome is involved in the innate immune response to amyloid-beta. *Nat Immunol*. 2008 Aug;9(8):857-865. doi: 10.1038/ni.1636. Epub 2008 Jul 11. PMID: 18604209; PMCID: PMC3101478.
65. Lee HM, Kim JJ, Kim HJ, Shong M, Ku BJ, Jo EK. Upregulated NLRP3 inflammasome activation in patients with type 2 diabetes. *Diabetes*. 2013 Jan;62(1):194-204. doi: 10.2337/db12-0420. Epub 2012 Oct 18. PMID: 23086037; PMCID: PMC3526026.
66. Mittal M, Siddiqui MR, Tran K, Reddy SP, Malik AB. Reactive oxygen species in inflammation and tissue injury. *Antioxid Redox Signal*. 2014 Mar 1;20(7):1126-1167. doi: 10.1089/ars.2012.5149. Epub 2013 Oct 22. PMID: 23991888; PMCID: PMC3929010.
67. Samuelsson M, Fisher L, Iverfeldt K. beta-Amyloid and interleukin-1beta induce persistent NF-kappaB activation in rat primary glial cells. *Int J Mol Med*. 2005 Sep;16(3):449-453. PMID: 16077954.
68. Shah FA, Kury LA, Li T, Zeb A, Koh PO, Liu F, Zhou Q, Hussain I, Khan AU, Jiang Y, Li S. Polydatin attenuates neuronal loss via reducing neuroinflammation and oxidative stress in rat mcao models. *Front Pharmacol*. 2019 Jun 26;10:663. doi: 10.3389/fphar.2019.00663. PMID: 31293416; PMCID: PMC6606791.
69. Bortolato B, Carvalho AF, Soczynska JK, Perini GI, McIntyre RS. The involvement of tnfr- α in cognitive dysfunction associated with major depressive disorder: An opportunity for domain specific treatments. *Curr Neuropharmacol*. 2015;13(5):558-576. doi: 10.2174/1570159x13666150630171433. PMID: 26467407; PMCID: PMC4761629.

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